

AN INVESTIGATION INTO ESSAY WRITING DIFFICULTIES OF ENGLISH-MAJOR STUDENTS AT HUFU

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ABSTRACT

Teaching and learning how to write in English is not an easy task for both teachers and students, especially how to write essays. Factually, writing essays is one of main parts in the writing course of English-major students at HUFU and the students need to be skillful enough to have good knowledge about essay writing skill for graduation. Although there has been countless research done by researchers to improve the essay writing skill among the learners, the English-major students at HUFU have still encountered a lot of enormous difficulties that cause an obstruction in achieving good writing products. As a result, in this paper, the writer primarily investigated into essay writing difficulties of HUFU English-major students in an attempt to come up with the possible solutions for dealing with the problems. The data were collected by means of some students' essays, interviews, and questionnaires. The results indicated that the students faced difficulties such as grammatical problems, coherence, cohesion, mother language transfer, a lack of ideas, and time constraint. Then the researcher suggested some possible ways in hope to solve these problems.

Key words: Writing skill, English essay writing, difficulties, solutions

1 Introduction

As writing is one the necessary means to communicate precisely in global interactions and business in general, it is studied as a main course by English-major students at HUFU. At university level, writing is used both as a standard system of communication and as a tool for acquiring knowledge. Grage & Kaplan (1996:24) show that “students in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) contexts will need English writing skills ranging from a simple paragraph and summary skills to the ability to write essays and professional articles.” It has been a common problem of English-major students at HUFU that they are incapable of expressing themselves in a clear, correct and comprehensive manner in essay writing. This is due to many factors. Raimes (1983:13) states that “when students complain about how difficult it is to write a second language, they are talking not only about the difficulty of finding the right words and using the correct grammar but also about the difficulty of finding and expressing ideas in a new language.” Therefore, the focus of this investigation is to identify the obstacles in writing English essays that

English-major students at HUFU face, and then suggest some corresponding solutions to deal with those problems.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The writing skill

Various researchers have paid attention to the study of writing, along with the other skill of language. Nunan (2003) defines:

Writing is both a physical and mental act. At the most basic level, writing is the physical act of committing words or ideas to some medium. On the other hand, writing is the mental work of inventing ideas, thinking about how to express them, and organizing them into statements and paragraphs that will be clear to a reader.

Moreover, Richards (2008) notes that learning how to write in either first or second language is one of the most difficult tasks students encounter. Kroll (2003) also observes that writing is a complex process involving the mastery of numerous skills that contribute to the overall difficulty of writing for any language learner. According to Hyland (2003), writing requires composing, which implies the ability either to tell pieces of information in the form of narratives or description, or transform information into new texts, as in expository or argumentative writing. Therefore, it is viewed as a continuum of activities that range from the more mechanical or formal aspects of writing to the more complex act of composing.

Similarly, according to Heaton (1979), the writing skill in a foreign language is complex and difficult to learn not only the ability to manipulate sentences and use language effectively whereas mechanical skill is the ability to use correctly those conventions peculiar to the written language such as punctuation and spelling. In fact, Harmer (2007) defines the writing skill is a process that should be carried out through different stages, including drafting, editing, planning and final draft. In other words, the writing skill is considered to consist of planning, reflection and the organization of ideas. Scholars regard the writing skill as a cognitive skill that writers are required not only to focus on sentence structure, lexical choices, spelling and punctuation, but also master the linguistic knowledge and integrate ideas coherently and cohesively in written discourse.

To sum up, writing is one of the most complicated skills in learning and practicing a language, for it is a productive skill that needs various competence such as linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence and discourse knowledge as well as knowledge about language use such as grammar, structure and vocabulary. As a result, language learners in general, English language learners in particular, might be faced with a variety of obstacles in the writing process; hence, these learners might also encounter the most prevalent essay writing difficulties. In the following section, the researcher intends to mention the problems related to the essay writing.

2.2 The difficulties of English essay writing

There are several aspects of difficulties that EFL students may have in EFL writing such as poor handwriting, poor spelling skills, or problems with grammar. On the other hand, in this review, the researcher would clarify two biggest problems like coherence and cohesion that students encounter in their English essay writing.

Firstly, Johns (1986:247) defines that coherence in written text is “a complex concept, involving a multitude of reader-and-text-based features”. Text-based features mean cohesion (i.e., the linking of sentences) and unity (i.e., sticking to the point). Reader-based features mean that the reader interacts with the text depending on his/her prior knowledge. Recently, coherence is defined as “an outcome of a dialogue between the text and its listener or reader” (Tanskanen & Benjamins, 2006:192). Besides, Kouch (2004) points out that coherence conveys the ability of the writer to combine sentences altogether in the text so that the reader is able to read and understand it easily. In other words, coherence is the ability to create meaningful correct sentences with the suitable choices of vocabulary items and following certain rules of word arrangement. Lee (2004:1) mentions that “low English proficiency students have difficulty making their writing coherent.... Many university students write incomprehensively”. In particular, the author lists some common essay writing problems as follows:

writing a paragraph without a topic sentence;

too specific controlling ideas;

difficulty in writing the thesis statement;

tendency on deviating from the controlling idea.

Another aspect is EFL essay writing cohesion. Many researchers agree that cohesion is related to linking ideas and connecting sentences and phrases. The importance of text cohesion is claimed that a text can stand as a text by means of cohesion. In fact, “the concept of cohesion is a semantic one; it refers to relations of meaning that exist within the text, and that define it as a text” (Halliday & Hasan, 1976:4). Baily (2003) notes that text cohesion refers to the clarity and readability in which writer needs to establish a link through the use of various cohesive devices such as reference, ellipsis, substitution, conjunctions and lexical cohesion. To conclude, British Council (2006:1) points out “some students take an eternity to produce a piece of writing as they are constantly rubbing out what they have written while at the opposite extreme the writing is done as fast as possible without any planning or editing”.

2.3 Factors causing poor EFL writing

Students’ essay writing difficulties result from many sources that are considered as lack of motivation, lack of reading, the impact of students’ first language into the target language, lack of time, writer’s block, and plagiarism.

The first problem is lack of motivation. For language learning, motivation is a key to get successful. Harmer (2006) emphasizes that many factors cause low motivation among learners, including the fear of failure in reflecting their knowledge about the language, the fear of making mistakes, and the uncertainty to show their productions. Needless to say, there are situations when students don't find themselves motivated enough to keep writing, however important the assignment may actually be. Obviously, it is a natural and wide-spread state that may be the result of many outside and inside reasons. To overcome this challenge, instructors need to establish writing habit among the students and encourage them to voice their thought.

Secondly, poor writing is also attributed to lack of reading. In fact, it is demonstrated that better readers are better writers. According to Raimes (1998:42) emphasizes that the more students read, the more they become familiar with the vocabulary, idiom, sentence patterns, organization flow, and cultural assumptions of native speakers of the language. In addition to writing strategies to raise the competence to write, reading is considered as the effective strategy to be followed and appreciated. In other words, lack of reading is among causes leading dissatisfaction in English essay writing.

In addition to the lack of motivation and reading, the impact of students' first language into the target language hinders students from writing. In fact, each culture has its own ways of organizing and perceiving speech and its own rhetorical conventions. Blanchard & Root (2004:203) states that writing remains difficult to acquire and each language has its own writing conventions that the writer needs to learn them without interfering with other language or languages. In some cases, it seems that students are unaware of English writing rules, and their mother language is activated in their minds instead of thinking in the target language. Therefore, they simply put words together to create their own writing work as the same way they do in their mother language. All in all, the influence of the first language is truly a obstacle in English essay writing.

Lack of time is also a common problem that harm students' ability to produce creative writing. There are many reason resulting in the lack of time such as unexpected incidents, personal problems, poor time management or anything else. The result is that students don't have enough time to complete the assignments.

Another reason for poor EFL writing is writer's block. As defined in Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, "writer's block is a condition, primarily associated with writing, in which an author loses the ability to produce new work, or experiences a creative slowdown. The condition ranges in difficulty from coming up with original ideas to being unable to produce a work for years". To some extent, writer's block can be seen as a feeling of impossibility to write due to some inner or outer reasons like depression, personal problems, or external distractions, severely obstructing one's ability to write for shorter or longer periods of time.

One more barrier causing students' low motivation in writing is plagiarism. In fact, plagiarism is a serious writing problem among most of the students. To put simply, the Internet development

makes students lazy to brainstorm and develop ideas in their own ways; students likely depend on sample essays. Consequently, students might feel that their abilities are just not enough to perform this or that academic assignment, and this may cause the lack of self-confidence. As a result, they might create discerning plagiarized materials to finish their assignments.

To sum up, research on the sources of EFL writing allows the researcher to easily identify difficulties in the process of English essay writing.

3 METHODOLOGY

The involved participants in this study were 76 second year English-major students. These students were taking part in the Writing 3 course, which focuses on English essay writing, after they finished the Writing 1 and 2 courses that train the students in sentence and paragraph writing skills. The participants need to learn how to achieve academic English essay writing not only as a compulsory subject of the English language curriculum but also as an English competence requirement for their future jobs. The Writing 3 course lasts for 30 in-class periods and 60 self-study periods, in which the students are required to write some types of essays such as process essays, cause/effect essays, comparison/contrast essays, and argumentative essays.

The investigator collected data by means of questionnaires, interviews, and students' essays. First, the questionnaires were designed to ask students about their difficulties in essay writing and factors affecting their writing, and then were handed out in class at the final in-class meeting. Second, an interview was given to the immediate teacher including open-ended questions to gain the teacher's feedback on students' essay writing. Finally, students' sample essays were employed to get a clear picture about the writing problems of the English-major students.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The questionnaires were delivered to the students at the middle of the course when they finished how to write three kinds of essays, including process essays, cause/effect essays, and comparison/contrast essays. The questionnaires consisted of two parts – the former was utilized to find out difficulties the students encounter in their English essay writing, and the latter asked about sources impacting on the students' writing. First, the students were directed to choose from suggested difficulties they meet. The results were demonstrated as in Table 1.

Table 1: Students' Essay Writing Difficulties

Essay Writing Difficulties	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Coherence	46	60.5
Cohesion	40	52.6
Writing a thesis statement	30	39.5

Essay Writing Difficulties	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Writing a conclusion	27	35.5
Lexis	45	59.2
Grammar	36	47.4
Spelling	15	19.7
Punctuation	13	17.1
Capitalization	11	14.5

As shown in Table 1, coherence is the most challenging problem (with more than 60%). Following coherence, 59.2% face difficulty in lexis, over 52% in cohesion, and over 47% in grammar. The students also meet other problems like writing a thesis statement and a conclusion. The challenges in spelling, punctuation, and capitalization are proven to hinder just a small number of the students.

The findings on factors affecting the students' writing show nearly 42% regard the lack of reading as the main source. About 35% admit that they lack motivation in writing practice. One more reason resulting in low writing is the impact of students' mother language on the second language, and nearly 30% agree with this. Besides, lack of time, writer's block and plagiarism are responded by a few students (as shown in Fig 1).

Fig 1: Chart Sources Affecting Essay Writing

When carrying out the interview with the incharge teacher, the researcher finds out the difficulties the teacher realized in the essay writing class, which include organizing ideas, choosing right words, coherence, and cohesion, etc. Moreover, the teacher observed the class during the process of practicing essay writing and learned that the students had low motivation, was lazy in reading, lacked vocabulary and used to express their thoughts as if they were translating word by word as in their own language. Hence, it comes clear to record that the results

in the questionnaires are reported as the same ideas said. In order for the learners to feel comfortable and write a sound essay, they are urgently encouraged to build their reading and writing habits since both skills are interrelated. The teacher agrees that reading is believed as an input for EFL learners.

Along with above findings, for the students' essays, the results shows that the students face the same problems when writing. An analysis of the students' essays unveils that students do not feel confident to convey thoughts, organize ideas improperly, use awkward grammar, lack coherence and cohesion.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

There are many challenges in coming up with a good essay that is easy to read and attractive to readers. In order to enhance essay writing skill among English-major students, there is a must for the researcher to come up with some solutions.

The first thing that need to be done is to create an environment that boosts learners to write down their thought. Reseachers show that writing tasks can be developed rapidly when students' concerns and interests are acknowledged, when they are given numerous opportunities to write and when they are encouraged to become participants. It is also pointed out that it is both 'reasonanle and motivating' to allow students to choose their own topics and that when students are allowed this freedom, their work is more successful and the quality of was better. As a result, teachers should insprire students by suggesting several topics and encourage them to find an aspect that may interest them.

Another way to help improve writing skills can be to encourage students to form reading habit. Students should be recommended to read a lot; in fact, reading will help them increase their knowledge of vocabulary, grammatical structures, knowledge of the world as well as writing style. Therefore, teachers should provide students with extensive reading materials and guide them how to solve with that in terms of reading and writing. However, when students read to get ideas, teachers should emphasize the risk of copying information and stress the consequences of plagiarism.

Furthermore, it is advisable that teachers should create a positive atmosphere by arranging students in pairs and groups to help students to get rid of the panic of writing and facilitate the writing task. It is further important for teachers to assign homework activities to promote their autonomy and responsibility. Students should be encouraged to overcome writer's block, thereby increasing writer's imagination and creativeness.

To solve the writing difficulties, students can be suggested using writing strategies such as free writing, journal writing, writing e-mails and diaries. What is more, it may be profitable if teachers add computer-based writing as a part of the course so that students are able to practice rapid drafting. Students should be motivated to learn how to use English collocation dictionaries in

their writing to enlarge their vocabulary and develop lexical usage. All in all, practicing the writing strategies can make students feel at ease to write their essays.

Finally, teachers need to spend a great deal of time checking, marking, and giving feedback to their students. Feedback is aimed to improve students' writing assignments. For instance, oral discussion between teachers and students are suggested for revising and correcting essays. Additionally, teachers should stimulate peer correction to train them to read critically, share ideas, and give comments. From these activities, students may learn something from their mistakes and get better.

6 CONCLUSION

To sum up, writing instructors should bear in mind that writing essays in English is not a simple task to do and requires much time and effort. Hence, the present study is an attempt to investigate major writing difficulties faced by English-major students at HUFU. Being familiar with the problems that HUFU English-major students have would help the instructors better understand students' writing and find useful ways to deal with them. EFL learners are subject to meet different difficulties that prevent them from writing effective essays. In addition, it has been found that less practice in reading, lack of motivation, impact of the first language, grammatical weakness, etc. were the main reasons resulting in essay writing problems. To remove this obstruction, it was recommended for both students and teachers to follow some given remedies.

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